

Improving Asteroid Family Age Estimation

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Abstract

Asteroids are orbiting objects created from the leftover material of the formation of the solar system. The collision of asteroids are important and informative phenomena in the evolution and history of our solar system. An asteroid family is the group of asteroids that result from an asteroid collision, with those related objects having similar orbits post-collision. By analyzing the current dynamical state of asteroid families, the properties of Near Earth Asteroids (NEAs), and the gradually non-negligible effect of sunlight on the asteroids over millions of years (the so-called Yarkovsky effect), we can estimate when the collision that generated each asteroid family happened. By creating a history of collisions in the solar system, we gain insights into how the solar system (and then other planetary systems) form and evolve. Also, we can understand the mechanisms that transport asteroids from the main belt to the near-Earth region. This project focuses on the calculations of the ages of different asteroid families within the Main Asteroid Belt. This effort consists of improving the uncertainties in our age estimation, testing different possibilities, such as (i) using a more recent data-set; (ii) improving the calibration of the Yarkovsky effect and comparing the results with previous studies. A more accurate age estimation will help us better understand the collisional evolution of our solar system.

1 Introduction

An asteroid family is the collection of asteroids that result from two asteroids colliding. The related objects have similar orbits post-collision, which is a key observation for the effects of this study. Proper elements can be considered constant over time and they permit the description of long-term evolution with a few parameters (Fenucci et al. 2022). In other words, proper values aren't the true parameters, but instead they are mediated or normalized over millions of years to remove perturbations due to planets or other effects. Asteroid families have the ability to inform us of collisions and effects hundreds of millions of years ago, as well as how the solar system will continue to behave or evolve in the future. One especially notable example are NEA's, which are ejected from the main asteroid belt and could impact our planet. However, there are numerous obstacles in obtaining accurate and useful estimates of these phenomena. Current estimations are constrained by our observational limitation of not being able to directly observe key parameters and characteristics of the asteroid family, for instance the family's average density.

The primary computation of the paper is the analysis of plots. The v-shape is plotted as a number of points representing asteroids and asteroid fragments, with one axis representing the semi-major axis and the other axis as the inverse of the object's diameter. Asteroid collisions naturally create a range of sizes and shapes of asteroid fragments, which lead to the spread of points on the y-axis. The spread along the x-axis, which is the drift from the original semi-major axis of the original asteroid family trajectory, is caused by the Yarkovsky effect, which results in the v-shape distribution of points plotted since the magnitude of the effect is related to the size of the object. The Yarkovsky effect is a phenomenon caused by light being absorbed and re-radiated (in this case photons from the sun hitting the asteroid fragments), which pushes the asteroid fragment in a certain direction. Although most of the graphs are v-shape in form, there are multiple classifications of families, dependent on their collision conditions or observable characteristics.

There are two primary classifications of asteroid families, fragmentation families and cratering families. As one might imagine, fragmentation families result from a collision between two relatively similar sized asteroids while a cratering family is from a small asteroid hitting a much larger asteroid, leaving a crater. The conventional threshold for classification is if the largest asteroid in the collision is less than (fragmentation) or greater than (cratering) 88% of the volume of the entire asteroid family.

There are two more labels that may be attached to asteroid families: young families and one-sided families. Young families can be either fragmentation or cratering, but the estimated age of the family is relatively young, which is defined to be less than 100 million years old. Due to the young age, the Yarkovsky effect has had less time to alter the trajectory of asteroid fragments within the family, and consequently, the inverse slopes of the young family graphs have lower values (the slope on the graph is steeper) than the other families. One sided families are families where one of the two sides of the V-shape is unidentifiable. One sided families, like young families, can also be either fragmentation or cratering type, though are more commonly fragmentation. It's possible that these families have had parent bodies that were ejected from the main asteroid belt by a resonance which also wiped out one of the sides, leaving only one for us to examine (Spoto et al. 2015).

There are currently two main models of the nature of the solar system's asteroid belt. One theory is that the main belt once had many more objects than it does currently. In fact, should this theory be true, the current amount of objects would be less than 1% of that from the beginning of the solar system. The reason for this would be objects being ejected from the main asteroid belt due to the gravitational effects of planets (mostly Jupiter and Saturn). In fact, we can trace some near-Earth asteroids (like Bennu, which will be discussed in more detail later in the paper) to a specific resonance in the belt. The second possibility is that at the beginning of the solar system, the main belt was completely or almost entirely empty, and that objects were implanted into the solar system due to gravitational effects and accumulated into the belt that exists today over time. Either of these two models could realistically lead to the current solar system. However, the main belt can inform which is more likely to be correct. By calculating estimates of the ages of these families, we can reconstruct the chronology of collisions. If there were many collisions and thus many families and objects that are very old, then the slow, gradual depletion of the belt theory makes more sense. Conversely, if there are very few old collisions, then the model of objects being absorbed into the belt over time is the more likely model. Although estimates for the ages have already been made in previous papers, the age estimates have large uncertainties.

By observing various families and exploring different possible parameters for calculation, our goal is to increase the accuracy of our estimation of ages and the magnitude of the Yarkovsky effect and in turn gain a better understanding of the history and current processes of the solar system. The paper will describe first relevant information and phenomena of the project, explain the process used to achieve results, and the significance of our findings.

2 Background and Methodology

2.1 Yarkovsky Effect

The Yarkovsky effect is the central phenomenon that makes our age estimation of asteroid families possible. The Yarkovsky effect is the result of light hitting an object (in this case sunlight acting on asteroid fragments) heating up a portion of that object. As the object rotates, the heat from the light exerts a slight thrust in a different direction, resulting in a net acceleration which in the short term isn't significant, but over millions of years noticeably alters the asteroid's orbit. As defined in by Novaković et al.(2022), the mathematical relationship between the asteroid's parameters and the strength of this effect can be expressed as:

$$\frac{da}{dt} \simeq \frac{da}{dt}_{Bennu} \times \frac{\sqrt{a_{Bennu}(1 - e_{Bennu}^2)}}{\sqrt{a}(1 - e^2)} \frac{D_{Bennu}}{D} \frac{\rho_{Bennu}}{\rho} \frac{\cos \phi}{\cos \phi_{Bennu}} \frac{1 - A}{1 - A_{Bennu}}$$

With this equation, the $\frac{da}{dt}$ on the right-hand side isn't constant, and depends on the object or family observed. The same can be said for the rest of the right hand side, which depends on various parameters (including density, bond albedo, obliquity, semi-major axis, and eccentricity) that are specific to the object in question. However, the $\frac{da}{dt}$ on the left-hand side should always be a consistent or similar value. We will discuss the asteroid's parameters in a later section. However, the main focus of the project is to estimate the distance that the object has traveled due to the Yarkovsky effect. We'll explain what the Bennu subtext within the equation refers to later in the paper.

2.2 Introduction of v-shape plots

The primary method for calculating the Δa is through plotting objects within a family on a graph with axes of proper semimajor axis and inverse diameter. If the family is old enough, the Yarkovsky effect dominates the spread of objects, which leads to the v-shape. The data of the diameters of each object is derived from the absolute magnitude of each fragment and assuming a common geometric albedo (average of known albedos observed in the WISE survey) for all asteroids and asteroid fragments within the family. Our first goal is to find how much the asteroid fragments have drifted from their original semi-major axis. We accomplish this by creating a line of best fit on both sides of the v-shape with the methodology outlined by Spoto et al. (2015). The plot of points (on each side) is divided horizontally into bins with a roughly similar point densities, and for each bin, the point with the highest deviation in proper semi-major axis value (or farthest out from the center with respect to the horizontal axis) is chosen as a data point in the linear regression. Although any of the other data points or objects near the center of the plot could also be used, the Yarkovsky effect did not fully act upon them and thus would skew our assumption that the Yarkovsky effect is the main and consistent phenomenon over time. As seen in Figure 1 below, the blue dots are the plotted fragments of the family, the circled dots are the selected representative point of each bin used for the linear fit, and the black lines are the resulting lines of best fit. For each data point, the residuals, their expected covariance, and the corresponding chi squared are calculated, and we assume that the error distribution has a normal distribution. Therefore, to exclude any point due to it being an outlier, we can compare the chi squared value of the post-fit residual with a threshold value of 10. Any point is considered an outlier and excluded from the line of best fit if the point's chi squared value is higher than the threshold value. After this, all outliers are recovered and used if their non-fitted residual is lower than a different threshold value, which in this case is 9. Finally, some points are manually removed if the WISE survey data provides evidence that the object was not a part of the family

Figure 1: Example v-shape plot.

The result we take from this line of best fit is the slope. More specifically, we'll take the inverse of the slope which represents the distance spanned by the asteroid family as a result of the Yarkovsky effect (note this is done independently for both of the two sides). We'll represent this as Δa . One key consideration when examining our results is how confident we are in the estimates of the slope, and consequently the inverse slope and calculated Δa value. In other words, whether the lines of best are stable or unstable. For instance, let's examine family 31 (the Euphrosyne family). With the

original value of the maximum inner diameter, 0.1499250375, we get the leftmost graph shown below. However, the left hand (inner) line of best fit does not appear to accurately represent the slope of the outer points. This observation is supplemented by an unusually high error for the inverse slope, at 0.0062777. Changing this initial value by small amounts has an effect on the output. This is an example of an unstable line of best fit. A stable line of best fit is ideal, as there is less ambiguity as to which of various possible estimates is correct. To check the unstable lines of best fit, we can manually observe the points on the outside to estimate how far along the inverse diameter axis we believe the slope would actually go, and test inputs approximating that value. The graphs probing family 31 are shown below. For this family in particular, the best inner diameter input was 0.179, with an inverse slope error of 0.002743.

Figure 2: Plots with various parameters for $\frac{1}{d_{max}}$ for Family 31.

3 Calculation of Family Ages

Returning to the bigger picture, our ultimate result will be the age of these families. We'll use the simple equation: family age = $\Delta a \div \frac{da}{dt}$. Where $\frac{da}{dt}$ is the left hand side of the equation:

$$\frac{da}{dt} \simeq \frac{da}{dt}_{Bennu} \times \frac{\sqrt{a_{Bennu}(1 - e_{Bennu}^2)}}{\sqrt{a}(1 - e^2)} \frac{D_{Bennu} \rho_{Bennu}}{D \rho} \frac{\cos \phi}{\cos \phi_{Bennu}} \frac{1 - A}{1 - A_{Bennu}}$$

And Δa is the inverse slope of the line of best fit. However, in order to find $\frac{da}{dt}$, we'll need various parameters of the asteroid family.

As previously mentioned, the necessary parameters of the asteroid and objects needed for the calculations are density, Bond albedo, obliquity, semi-major axis, and eccentricity. Perhaps the biggest limitation of this project is the observational inability to directly observe or extrapolate the actual parameters of objects in the main asteroid belt. However, as these values are critical in estimating the Yarkovsky effect and thus the age of the asteroid family, our estimates should be as accurate as possible. The primary method of getting values is through the use of NEA's. NEA's are useful data points for our estimations because many of them originated from the Main Asteroid Belt due to the previously mentioned ejection effect. We'll use two NEA's as our samples, which we'll apply to the families when calculating the $\frac{da}{dt}$. These asteroids are Bennu and Apophis. Bennu has been used as an NEA estimate in other studies such as (Spoto et al. 2015), however it was recently discovered that Bennu is a more complex asteroid than originally expected. It is active and ejecting matter, which may adversely affect the estimation and confidence of our Yarkovsky effect estimate. For this reason, we'll be using Apophis as well. The parameter values used in the calculations are listed below in Table 1 with values taken from Spoto et al. (2015), Farnocchia et al. (2013), Hernandez et al. (2022), Dzaidura et al. (2022), and NASA JPL's Small-Body Database. By comparison, Apophis has an incredibly promising Yarkovsky effect determination, which is derived from its signal to noise ratio of value to uncertainty. A value greater than five is considered a good value, and Apophis has one

of around 200. We'll also be comparing the $\frac{da}{dt}$ calculated with Apophis parameter to that of Bennu. When starting this project, our initial goal was to show that the $\frac{da}{dt}$ of Apophis would be within three sigmas (standard deviations) of Bennu's. However, we ultimately find that the $\frac{da}{dt}$ of Bennu is approximately twice that of Apophis. This implies that the $\frac{da}{dt}$ is not consistent across asteroids as we assumed it should be. One possible explanation for this finding is the fact that Bennu is an active asteroid, and that the active elements would alter the Yarkovsky effect over time. In any case, given that using Bennu or Apophis values will lead to different ages, comparing previous estimates of ages to our results can provide insights into the asteroids themselves.

	Yark. effect	diameter	semi-major axis	eccentricity	obliquity	density	Bond albedo
symbol (units)	$\frac{da}{dt}$ ($\frac{AU}{d^2}$)	D (km)	a (AU)	e	Φ (deg)	ρ ($\frac{g}{cm^3}$)	$1 - A$
Bennu	-19×10^4	0.565	1.133	0.204	$\frac{175\pi}{180}$	1.26	0.983
Apophis	-19.03×10^4	0.34	0.9227	0.19144	$\frac{176\pi}{180}$	1.194	0.9097

Table 1: Bennu and Apophis Parameters Used

4 Age Estimates and Results

For our results we'll focus on a few select families that exemplify the approach taken to age estimation and the takeaways we can draw. Let's first continue with the cratering asteroid Family 31, Euphrosyne, which we saw plotted previously. When calculating the family age with Bennu values, the output is an inner age of $875 \pm 4.8myr$ and an outer age of $752 \pm 0.64myr$. Using the Apophis values, the inner age is $1564 \pm 8.58myr$ while the outer age is $1343 \pm 1.16myr$. The previously estimated value was $1309 \pm 302myr$. We can observe two key points. First, the deviations in our new calculations appear to have significantly reduced standard deviations. However, this is not actually the case, it only appears to be because the code solely takes into account the uncertainty based off of the fit. In reality, the uncertainty of the various parameters and other estimations also need to be accounted for, which would add about 20% of the total as a fixed standard deviation. Recall that this constraint fundamentally stems from our inability to directly measure parameters of objects in the main belt that are used in the Yarkovsky determination. Second, we notice that the age calculated with the Apophis parameters (approximately 1564 and 1343 *myr*) is much closer to the originally estimated 1309 *myr* than the Bennu age estimate (approximately 875 or 753 *myr*). One possible explanation for this discrepancy is that Family 31 is more similar to Apophis than Bennu in its properties. For instance, Bennu is a B-type, implying a heavy presence of carbon and volatiles, whereas Apophis is an S-type asteroid, meaning it is likely stony or minerally. However for a different family, like Family 10, the Bennu estimates are 950 and 979 *myr* and the Apophis values were 1697 and 1749 *myr*. The original estimate was 1330*myr* with a deviation of 300 *myr*. In this case, given that the age of the family sits almost perfectly in between our two estimates, this family could plausibly be spectral B-type or S-type or some entirely separate spectral type. Alternatively, it could be an active asteroid similar to Bennu, but simply less complex or less active, which in turn would lead to less of a change in the Yarkovsky effect, resulting in an age estimate between those of Bennu and Apophis. Overall, we cannot conclude that the asteroids in the belt have parameters or spectral type that resemble the NEA solely based on the similarity of age estimations. However, there is almost certainly a link between the spectral composition and the parameters of the objects to the Yarkovsky effect, evidenced by the difference in the different Yarkovsky effect estimations of Bennu and Apophis. Future data of other NEA's with a variety of spectral types may yield different age estimations that could provide more data on age estimates, and hopefully provide insight into the true relationship between the asteroid family's spectral type or other defining characteristics and the Yarkovsky effect.

Table 2 represents the age estimations for Family 158 and in this case, the Bennu age estimates are the values that better approximate the previously estimated values. Returning to our first observation on standard errors, although the code's standard deviations are deceiving, we still have an overall decrease in standard deviation even after adjusting for the error of the various parameters, using the 20% approximation mentioned previously. Using the age estimates that line up with the previously calculated value, as seen in Table 3, we see that in most of our results, the standard deviation did reduce slightly.

	Inner	σ_{inner}	Outer	σ_{outer}
Bennu	1721	23.624	1310	9.247
Apophis	3074	42.200	2339	16.517
Previous est.	1792	444	1708	399

Table 2: Family 158 (Fragmentation) Age Estimates in *myr*

Family and Side	Prior Estimate	σ_{prior}	Calculated Estimate	$\sigma_{adjusted}$
31 (Apophis) Inner	1309	312	1564	321.38
31 (Apophis) Outer	1160	272	1343	269.76
158 (Bennu) Inner	1792	444	1721	367.82
158 (Bennu) Outer	1708	399	1310	271.25

Table 3: Comparisons of values and σ to prior estimates in *myr*

In conclusion, although we had initially hoped that the estimations using Bennu and Apophis would yield similar Yarkovsky calibrations and similar family ages, our results show that estimates made using the two different NEA’s yield different age values. Additionally, in most calculations, there was a slight reduction in standard error compared to previously made estimates.

In the bigger picture, despite the existence of relatively old asteroid families in our results, (in our examples, notably Family 10 and Family 158), we cannot eliminate or prove either model of the asteroid belt mentioned in the introduction. We have not identified all possible families within the belt, and our method of family classification is not exact enough. However, our results are still useful; having an understanding of when a collision occurred and family was created implies that each object in the family was present since the impact, and our estimations provide a different set of possible estimations and errors from NEA’s. The final goal would be to draw data from the presence of these asteroid family members and relate them to formation scenarios. As we continue to get better, more accurate data, such as the recent OSIRIS mission for Bennu and the scheduled mission for Apophis in 2029, calculations will become more informed and estimations will have lower errors until we are able to gain more insights and draw definitive conclusions. Ultimately, we will have a better understanding of the Yarkovsky effect, a history of asteroid collisions within our solar system and the resulting families, and how NEA’s and other objects behave as a result of this phenomenon.

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6 Citations

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